

Supplementary table 1

Citrullinated peptide antigens on the multiplex microarray

Antigen	Protein	(amino acids) Amino acid sequence	References
Cit-peptide 1	hnRNP-A3	pending patent application	*
Cit-peptide 5	hnRNP-A3	pending patent application	*
Cit-peptide Bla26	hnRNP-A3	pending patent application	*
Cit-peptide Z1	hnRNP-A3	pending patent application	*
Cit-peptide Z2	hnRNP-A3	pending patent application	*
Cit-C1	CII	(355-378) (GPO) ₅ -GLOGA CIT GLTG CIT OGDAGPQGKVGPS-(GPO) ₂ -GKKYG	1
Cit-F4 _(Cit-Cit)	CII	(916-939) (GPO) ₅ -GDKGEAGEOGE CIT GLKGH CIT GFTGLQ-(GPO) ₂ -GKKYG	2
Cit-F4 _(Cit-R)	CII	(916-939) (GPO) ₅ -GDKGEAGEOGE CIT GLKGHRGFTGLQ-(GPO) ₂ -GKKYG	2
Cit-F4 _(R-Cit)	CII	(916-939) (GPO) ₅ -GDKGEAGEOGERGLKGH CIT GFTGLQ-(GPO) ₂ -GKKYG	2
CEP-1	α -enolase	(5-21) C-KIHAC CITE IFD SCIT GNPTVE-C	3
Cit-Fib α ₃₆₋₅₀	fibrinogen α	(36-50) GPC CIT VVE CIT HQSACKDS	4-6
Cit-Fib α ₅₆₃₋₅₈₃	fibrinogen α	(563-583) HHPGIAEFPS CIT GKSSSYSKQF	7, 8
Cit-Fib α ₅₈₀₋₆₀₀	fibrinogen α	(580-600) SKQFTSSTSYNC CIT GDSTFESKS	8, 9
Cit-Fib- α ₆₂₁₋₆₃₅	fibrinogen α	(621-635) CIT GHAKS CIT PV CIT GIHTS	4-6
Cit-Fib β ₃₆₋₅₂	fibrinogen β	(36-52) NEEGFFSA CIT GHRPLDKK	10
Cit-Fib β ₆₀₋₇₄	fibrinogen β	(60-74) CIT PAPPISGGGY CIT CIT	4-6
cfc1-cyc (CCP1)	filaggrin	(304-324) HQCHQEST CIT GRSRGRCGRSGS	11
Cit-Vim ₂₋₁₇	vimentin	(2-17) STCIT SVSSSSY CIT CIT MFGG	12
Cit-Vim ₆₀₋₇₅	vimentin	(60-75) VYAT CIT SSAV CIT LC CIT SSVP	10

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CII = collagen type II; Cit/CIT = citrullinated/citrulline; hnRNP-A3 = heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein A3

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